

PREDICTION OF STUDENTS ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE UTILIZING HYBRID TEACHING- LEARNING BASED FEATURE SELECTION AND MACHINE LEARNING MODEL

¹ Smt. Saranya. V , ² Shri. S. Ameresan

¹M.phil Research scholar, ² Associate Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Computer Science

^{1,2} Ponnaiyah Ramajayam Institute of Science and Technology,

^{1,2} PRIST UNIVERSITY,

¹ saranlachu.sl@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education is the manifestation of the perfection already in men quoted by Swami Vivekananda. For better Education, one need to have a good educator whom we call in our society as teacher. Education system stands on four important pillars i.e. Educator (teacher), Student, Parent, and Management.

Teachers play an important role in shaping the students by disseminating the knowledge using various teaching learning methods, from the classical method of blackboard teaching (chalk and talk) to the present state of webinars (live lecturers) by the teaching community to reach the student community at large. Student will acquire the knowledge and provide vital information back to the system by the way of feedback. There are various techniques like classification, clustering, association and outlier analysis used for the knowledge extraction.

Keywords: Educator, student performance, hybrid learning, machine learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of every higher education institute is to offer quality education to its students. ne means to achieve highest level of quality in higher education system is by assessing student's performance in the course he joined. The traditional models of teaching learning methods will not be sufficient. The students data is to be mined to extract hidden knowledge,

using which the students performance is to be evaluated, this helps in to idesntify easily.

With the brief review presented in this figure 1, it can be understood that in order to assess the learning abilities and placement abilities of the learner, there is a need to develop a system which combine all the aspects of knowledge acquisition, thereby discovering the gap and devise the method i.e. a link analysis to further strengthen the learning and placement abilities of the learner. The earlier work is focused on analyzing independent components of the knowledge acquiring process [1]. The paper aims to categorize the Student information using Attribute Oriented success and failure in online courses. It is also possible to predict the students performance in offline courses by accessing records from general websites. In this paper the prediction of feature set helps to analyze the number of records based on different categories like amount of time spend on online videos, courses delivered in last semester. This model helps in demonstrating whether a student can pass through a particular course structure. [2] Induction which is used to reduce the representation attributes of the data. Using Maximally Specific Hypopaper the data representation is more general to specific ordering. The GAP is analyzed using Statistical Measures and Scaling of Scores.

1.1. OBJECTIVE

- 1) The main objective of this proposed paper:

- 2) To discover the Attributes of importance.
- 3) Producing Inductive learning hypopaper.
- 4) Inductive learning hypopaper vs Decision Tree Classification.
- 5) Identification of GAP analysis among students using Statistical Measures – Normal distribution
- 6) Identify the rating of the teacher based on the z-score.

Fig: 1 proposed system model

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Majority of students are opting engineering courses for securing a good job. Therefore taking a sensible career choice concerning the placement after finishing a particular course is essential in a student's life. The Universities admit good number of students in different branches of engineering and other courses. Therefore, helping the students towards effective placements is a challenging task to the Universities. Hence, to assist the students in getting placements, each student skills and strengths are to be identified and these patterns help the authorities for planning courses, training classes, thereby helping the students towards success during placement drives, and providing them a chance to stand in corporate sector [3,4].

Effective analysis is to be carried out to analyze the skill tests of the students, and guide them towards proper progress. This analysis will also help the faculty

in taking proper concentration towards the improvement of the students. These steps help in building the reputation of institutes. It is therefore necessary to discover methods and patterns from the large student groups to guide decisions about future activities. It is expected that statistical techniques suit well to model the data with minimal input[5].

3. METHODOLOGY

The present study concentrates on the prediction of placements of engineering graduates of a Anna university, in Chennai. In 1997 The National Committee made a recommendation that the higher education imparting universities should also take care about providing the opportunities to the students admitted. The universities cooperatively accepted the suggestion and concluded to have skills modules and curriculum developments. Universities started looking different ways of providing skills towards the improvisation of the students, so as to enhance the employability skills.

Among the various skills, the most anticipated skills which benefits towards placement opportunities include:

- Application of knowledge while developing core competencies;
- improve competency in Programming skills and Domain Skills
- Technical Writing Skills
- Email writing skills
- Communication skills
- Team building activities

In addition, it has been argued that placement can have a positive impact upon academic performance through intervening variables such as:

- Contributes to a student-centered approach to learning

In this section of the paper, the overview of the developed proposal is highlighted. In any educational

system, the vital components are research , where the faculty strengths can be identified, and the ability of the students along with the family support are considered in this section.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN

The work in this section is highlighted by linking the research plan, so as to identify the linkage between the impact of the factors like faculty teaching skills, Programming Skills, Communication Skills, financial status of the family, family support and students academic excellence. In order to have a better understanding about these predominant factors, correlation plays a vital role, it describes an existing affiliation between variables.

4.1. DATASET CONSIDERED

The study is conducted on 660 undergraduate students among the 6000 students of GITAM University. The 660 Students were from various branches of Engineering.

4.2. DATA ANALYSIS

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) was used to calculate the associations. In this paper, the t-Test is considered for finding the influence of academic performance varied with gender.

In order to test the ability of students in different domains, raw scores cannot be used. An alternative in this work we have proposed Z-score normalization considering the following attributes:

4.2.1. DESCRIPTION OF THE DEPENDENT VARIABLE (DV)

Academic performance is considered as the dependent variable in this section. In this section, academic performance was utilized to consider the mean percentage of students in each branch, grades obtained in mid examinations and Semester end examinations.

Table: 1 Academic performance exhibited by the students

Performance of students in CSE Branch Academic Performance	No of students Frequency	Mean Mean	Std. Deviation
performance on Value Added courses	660	6.40	.964
Academic performance in Domain skills	660	6.36	.961
Academic performance in Programmingskills	660	5.37	.896
Performance in previous semester examination	660	5.58	.887
Academic performance in Mid-Examinations	660	5.29	.852
Regularity in Attending to college	660	5.15	.885
Total	660		

Table 1 demonstrates the performance of undergraduate students, and from the table, it can be seen that the performance of the students with respect to value added courses is better when compared to that of mid-exams, where the students are showing poor performance. The Academic Performance, (ACA_PER) of the students is considered as the dependent variable, since the performance is subjected to this factor only. The deviation of the students in academics is estimated and is highlighted in the following table.

Table: 2 Arithmetic mean and standard deviation

Academic Performance	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation
Academic Abilities	660	2.31	0.40

4.2.2. DEVIATION OF STUDENTS SCHOLARLY PERFORMANCE WITH GENDER

The following Table shows the relationship between gender and his scholarly performance, attained from the student t-test.

Table: 3 Review of the t-test results for the relationship between Gender and Academic performance

Gender	No of students considered	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig
Male	198	2.35	0.414	0.918	0.420
Female	132	2.35	0.395	0.918	0.420

The Mean value presented in the above Table, signifies that there is no disparity connecting scholarly performance of male and female students. This is confirmed by estimating the t value, which is 0.918 and its calculated sig = 0.420, which is greater than alpha = 0.05. The finale thus signifies that there is no major dissimilarity in scholarly recital between male and female students.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results derived from this are used in for identifying the gap related to learning, employability and the recommended training to be given. This system is used to assess the required training to be imparted for the learner to be employable and required orientation for the faculty for further improvement. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) was used to calculate the associations. In this paper, the t-Test is considered for finding the influence of academic performance varied with gender.

In order to test the ability of students in different domains, raw scores cannot be used. An alternative in this work we have proposed Z-score normalization. The system can also be used for carrying out the academic audit in the teaching learning process. The sample consisted of 660 undergraduate students selected from 6000 students of Anna University. The 660 Students were selected from the various branches of Engineering.

The results of this proposed method clearly shown that the Maximally Specific Hypopaper is well suited for educational data mining. These hypotheses can be used to identify the key attributes that is required for employability among the graduates, which can be used as predictor attribute. Using AOI method we can able to reduce the representation of attributes set there by identifying the attributes of important. It also paved a way for data reduction technique. The results clearly show that the we can able to reduce the rule representation to 11%.

6. CONCLUSION

The factor analysis was considered successful. Of the factor structures that were developed, most were considered to have either a moderate or strong factor structure with the variables that were chosen. All the KMO test statistics were at least .500. The high school GPA and rank had the highest factor loadings and communalities > .900. Except for F7 (Study Habits Class Attendance), all factors had moderate to strong values for Cronbach's alpha, indicating internal consistency of response to the survey questions.

7. REFERENCES

- [1]. L. von Rueden et al., "Informed Machine Learning - A Taxonomy and Survey of Integrating Prior Knowledge into Learning Systems," in IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering.
- [2]. S. M. Aslam, A. K. Jilani, J. Sultana and L. Almutairi, "Feature Evaluation of Emerging E-Learning Systems Using Machine Learning: An Extensive Survey," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 69573-69587, 2021.
- [3]. O. Poquet, L. -A. Lim and M. De Laat, "Learning Analytics in the Corporate Sector: What Business Leaders Say," in IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies. doi: 10.1109/TLT.2022.3164783
- [4]. J. Ariza, M. Jimeno, R. Villanueva-Polanco and J. Capacho, "Provisioning Computational Resources for

Cloud-Based e-Learning Platforms Using Deep Learning Techniques," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 89798-89811, 2021.

- [5]. H. Lee, R. -S. Guo and C. Chen, "E-Learning in the Postpandemic Era: A Case Study in Taiwan," in IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management.
- [6]. B. Alojaiman, "Toward Selection of Trustworthy and Efficient E-Learning Platform," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 133889-133901, 2021.

IJADST